

THERMAL DECARBOXYLATION OF CHLOROBENZOIC ACIDS

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Thermal decarboxylation of *o*-chloro- and 2,4-dichlorobenzoic acids in resorcinol solution follows S_{E2} mechanism. The activation energies, frequency factors and entropies of activation are: 32300 cal. mole⁻¹, 6.76×10^{10} sec.⁻¹ and -12.0 cal. deg.⁻¹ for *o*-chlorobenzoic acid, and 27600 cal. mole⁻¹, 3.98×10^{10} sec.⁻¹ and -17.6 cal. deg.⁻¹ for 2,4-dichlorobenzoic acid.

In continuation of our work on benzoic acid (this *Journal*, 1954, 31, 726) we present the results of our studies on *o*-chloro- and 2,4-dichlorobenzoic acids.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

The apparatus was the same as reported earlier and the procedure was also similar excepting that instead of reading the total volume of CO₂ evolved at the completion of reaction, Guggenheim's method (*Phil. Mag*, 1926, 2, 538) was employed to obtain the first order rate constants. Two series of values, V^t and $V^{t'}$, for the volumes of carbon dioxide at times t and t' , separated by a constant interval Δt , were obtained at different times ' t '. A plot of $\log_{10}(V^t - V)$ against ' t ' gave a straight line, the slope of which was equal to $0.4343 \times$ rate constant. Typical data on decarboxylation of *o*-chlorobenzoic acid in resorcinol at 237° are shown in Table I.

TABLE I

Time (t).	V of CO ₂ at t .	V^t of CO ₂ at ($t + \Delta t$).	Diff. ($V^t - V$).	Log ($V^t - V$).
0 min.	0.6 c.c.	19.4 c.c.	18.8 c.c.	1.2742
2	12.3	26.8	15.5	1.1903
4	19.4	32.4	13.0	1.1139
6	26.3	37.6	11.3	1.0531
8	31.4	40.6	9.2	0.9638
10	38.6	46.2	7.6	0.8808
12	41.6	48.1	6.5	0.8129
14	45.2	50.6	5.4	0.7324

The plot of $\log (V^t - V)$ against t gave a straight line, the slope of which, when multiplied by 2.303 and divided by 60, provided the rate constant as 143.95×10^{-5} sec.⁻¹ at 237°. Further determinations at this temperature furnished the values: 134.21, 115.83, 126.48, 123.74 ($\times 10^{-5}$). The mean of these five (128.84×10^{-5} sec.) was taken to be the rate constant at 237°. Similar data were collected for *o*-chlorobenzoic acid at three other temperatures (249°, 224° and 218°). The same procedure was repeated for 2,4-dichlorobenzoic acid at 192°, 201°, 211° and 220°. Table II records the values of rate constants for the two acids at different temperatures.

TABLE II

<i>o</i> -Chlorobenzoic acid.		2:4-Dichlorobenzoic acid.	
Temp.	Rate const. $k \times 10^5$ per sec	Temp.	Rate const. $k \times 10^5$ per sec.
218°	37.58	192°	52.72
224°	55.66	201°	91.41
237°	128.84	211°	166.08
249°	255.02	220°	280.50

The plot of $\log k$ vs. $1/T$ was used in deriving the activation energies of the two acids. The frequency factors, A , were computed with the help of the Arrhenius equation:

$$k = A.e^{-E/RT}$$

substituting the experimental values of the rate constants k and activation energies, E . The thermodynamic characteristics of activation were calculated from the following relations (using the notations of Glasstone, Laidler and Eyring, "The Theory of Rate Processes"):

$$\Delta F^\ddagger = 2.303 RT \log (RT/Nhk)$$

$$\Delta S^\ddagger = (\Delta E^\ddagger - \Delta F^\ddagger)/T$$

In these calculations the heat of activation $\Delta E^\ddagger$ was taken to be equal to $(E - RT)$ where E is the experimental activation energy.

The activation energies, frequency factors, free energies and entropies of activation are shown in Table III.

TABLE III

	<i>o</i> -Chlorobenzoic acid.	2:4-Dichlorobenzoic acid.
Activation energy ^a (E)	32300 cal. mole ⁻¹	27600 cal. mole ⁻¹
Frequency factor (A)	6.76×10^{10} sec ⁻¹	3.98×10^8 sec ⁻¹
Free energy of activation (at 493°K) ($\Delta F^\ddagger$)	37200 cal. mole ⁻¹	35300 cal. mole ⁻¹
Entropy of activation (at 493°K) ($\Delta S^\ddagger$)	-12.0 cal. deg. ⁻¹	-17.6 cal. deg. ⁻¹

DISCUSSION

The results presented above clearly show that like benzoic acid (*loc. cit.*), *o*-chloro- and 2:4-dichlorobenzoic acids are unstable in acidic solution, indicating that these acids undergo thermal decarboxylation through a bimolecular mechanism, involving the electrophilic replacement of $(\text{COOH})^+$ from the acid:

A comparison of the three acids reveals that whilst benzoic acid decarboxylates at 255° with a velocity of only 30.3×10^{-5} sec.⁻¹, the extrapolated values at this temperature for *o*-chloro- and 2:4-dichlorobenzoic acids are 375×10^{-5} and 966×10^{-5} respectively. Further, the activation energies for these acids progressively decrease from 42500 (benzoic acid) and 32300 (*o*-chlorobenzoic acid) to 27600 cal. (2:4-dichlorobenzoic acid). This

may be explained on the assumption that S_{12} mechanism is facilitated by a high electron density on the α -carbon. The presence of chlorine in the *ortho* (or *para*) position increases the negative character of the α -carbon, which therefore attracts the proton or protonated solvent more readily, and undergoes decarboxylation rapidly. Further, the presence of two chlorine atoms in *ortho* and *para* positions in the 2:4-dichlorobenzoic acid enhances the negativity of the α -carbon, and hence, the latter acid decomposes much faster than the *ortho*-acid. This explanation is directly in line with the views of Brown, Hammick and Scholefield (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 778). The other explanation which is helpful here is that of Schubert (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 71, 2639) who suggests that due to the presence of substituents, the resonance interaction of the carboxyl with the ring is inhibited, which leads to the weakening and consequent breaking of the bond between carboxyl and the α -carbon.

Now we may also compare the frequency factors and activation entropies of benzoic acid ($8.7 \times 10^{12} \text{ sec}^{-1}$ and $+2.1 \text{ cal. deg.}^{-1}$ at 255°), calculated from the data of our previous paper (*loc. cit.*) with *o*-chloro- and 2:4-dichlorobenzoic acids, shown in Table III. The continuous decrease in these values indicates a continuous fall in the steric factor which determines the probability of reaction. This is similar to the observation of Brown *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) and may be explained on the assumption of a steric effect. The chlorine atom in the *ortho* position, while enhancing the negativity of the α -carbon, may itself try to attract the proton, which means that the attack on the α -carbon will not be so facile as pictured earlier. Further, in 2:4-dichlorobenzoic acid the two chlorine atoms present are likely to inhibit to a greater extent the approach of the proton to the α -carbon, thus accounting for still lower frequency factor and lower entropy of activation.

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